

The impact of cell wall polysaccharides on cassava's cooking ability

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ABSTRACT

Cassava plays a crucial role in food security in rural Africa and Latin America as a staple crop and a key carbohydrate source. To enhance its nutritional value and resilience to climate change, pests, and diseases, the RTBfoods project is developing improved varieties that are more adaptable and sustainable. This study, conducted as part of RTBfoods Phase II, investigates the influence of cell wall polysaccharides (CWP) and starch composition on cassava texture post-cooking. Using MID-IR spectroscopy and physicochemical analyses, it was demonstrated that pectin solubilization, hemicellulose degradation, and starch modifications strongly influence texture. Firm varieties (e.g., HMC1) maintained rigid textures due to strong lignins-xylose interactions, which reinforced cell wall integrity and reduced polysaccharide solubilization. Adhesive/mealy varieties (e.g., PER183, COL1505) retained branched polysaccharides, impacting textural perception by enhancing cohesion and adhesiveness. Friable varieties (e.g., CR63, IND135) exhibited greater solubilization of structural components, leading to weaker, crumbly textures. MID-IR spectroscopy successfully identified key spectral changes in the C=O and C-O vibrational regions, confirming structural transformations in pectins, hemicelluloses, and starch. These findings confirm that texture is not solely dependent on starch content but is significantly influenced by starch-pectin-hemicellulose interactions. This study highlights MID-IR spectroscopy as a rapid, non-destructive tool for cassava quality assessment, providing valuable insights for breeding programs and food processing optimization. Integrating these findings into cassava breeding strategies will help develop varieties with improved textural properties that meet both industrial and consumer expectations.

Key Words: Cassava, RTBfoods, MID-IR spectroscopy, starch, pectin, texture, polysaccharides, cooking, breeding, consumer preferences.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Context

Food security in rural Africa relies heavily on nutrient-rich staple crops such as roots, tubers, and bananas (RTB), including cassava roots and plantain bananas. These crops play a vital role in sustaining communities, providing essential carbohydrates and energy. To further enhance their nutritional value and resilience to diseases, continuous efforts have led to the development of improved crop varieties.

The RTBfoods project ("Breeding RTB Products for End-User Preferences") was launched in 2017 to develop high-throughput phenotyping tools to improve varietal selection and ensure that new varieties align with consumer preferences, particularly in texture and processing qualities, thereby maximizing adoption and impact. Now part of the OneCGIAR RTB breeding project (2023–2024), this initiative leverages innovative breeding approaches, including high-throughput phenotyping and spectral analysis, to accelerate the development of high-quality RTB crops.

By placing consumer needs at the center of breeding efforts, RTBfoods contributes to greater acceptance of improved varieties, strengthening food security, nutrition, and agricultural sustainability in rural African communities.

1.2 Objectives and hypothesis

Cassava, rich in starch, is commonly consumed boiled. Its post-cooking texture is influenced by factors such as variety, maturity stage, and cooking method. However, Texture variations among cassava varieties are not solely dependent on starch content but also on the molecular structure of starch (amylose-to-amylopectin ratio) and its interactions with cell wall polysaccharides. (Sajeev et al., 2010). Moreover, cell wall polysaccharides (CWP) are known to play a major role in determining the physical and nutritional properties of fruits and vegetables (Liu et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2005). The hypothesis proposed here is that CWPs particularly pectin, could be a key factor influencing the texture of cooked cassava. Therefore, the objective of this study was to specifically investigate the influence of CWP and starch composition on the texture of cooked cassava.

This study, conducted within the framework of the second phase of the RTBfoods project, focuses on cassava, a crop central to African diets. It aims to identify the physicochemical characteristics and mechanisms that influence texture, one of the most critical quality traits for consumers.

The research specifically analyses:

- The physicochemical composition (e.g., cell wall composition i.e. pectins, , lignins, starch) of cassava varieties exhibiting contrasting cooking behaviors.
- The use of Mid-infrared spectroscopy Mid-IR to complement biochemical results and enhance the analysis of cassava composition, enabling a rapid and non-destructive assessment of key traits linked to texture and quality.
- The texture variations between raw and boiled cassava, as well as among different cassava varieties, and establishes the relationship between these texture variations and the specific biochemical composition of each variety.

The findings will enhance our understanding of texture-related mechanisms and guide the development of cassava varieties that better meet consumer expectations.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Material

For this study, eight cassava varieties grown at CIAT (Colombia) in 2023 and harvested in March 2024 were prepared under standardized conditions at CIRAD in Montpellier and CIAT in Cali (Colombia). The varieties were analyzed in their raw state and after boiling in water for 20 and 30 minutes. The analyses focused on sensory quality (at CIAT). Sensory evaluations focused on descriptive texture attributes such as friability, glassiness, hardness, moisture, crumbliness and stickiness. Mechanical texture (texture-extrusion SOP) was assessed for 5 varieties only (because three of the eight varieties did not grow enough roots) (at CIAT), on the basis of CP+F (Count Peaks+ F), Ldist (Linear Distance F-T 1:4), CP-F (Count Peaks- F), Area.F (Area F-T 1:4), MaxF (Max Force), and GFT (Gradient F-T 1:2). D.MaxF (Distance at Max Force), (End force at 20mm (g)). Fresh roots of the eight varieties were sent to CIRAD, where part of them were frozen fresh (-80°C), while another part was boiled for 30 minutes, then frozen (-80°C).

Tableau 1: Sensory texture results after 20 minutes of boiling, provided by CIRAD, Montpellier, France.

	Friability	Glassiness	Hardness	Moisture	Mealiness	Stickiness
COL1516	7,1	2,4	3,4	3,1	6,7	7,0
CR63	6,1	1,5	2,5	2,4	7,7	7,2
HMC1	1,3	4,5	7,9	7,0	3,2	1,7
IND135	8,5	1,6	1,3	1,4	8,0	7,1
COL2215	4,9	2,7	4,6	3,5	6,4	5,5
PER183	4,0	3,0	4,1	3,3	6,5	5,6
COL1505	5,6	3,7	3,4	3,0	7,0	6,2
SM1127	4,5	2,3	4,3	2,6	7,3	6,8

Tableau 2: Mechanical texture results provided by CIRAD, Montpellier, France.

	GFT (g/sec)	MaxF (g)	D.MaxF (mm)	EndF (g)	Area.F (g.sec)	Ldist (g.sec)	CP+F (g)	CP-F (g)
COL1516	2263	13908	20	13711	69025	15337	2	2
HMC1	2753	19191	15	16918	130902	26792	3	3
IND135	811	12662	20	12624	54455	12143	1	1
PER183	2249	16576	19	16499	92216	17408	2	2
SM1127-8	2171	17627	20	17575	97403	18664	2	2

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Samples Preparation

Grinding

The samples, which had been received frozen at -20°C (following transport in a cold box from CIRAD Montpellier to INRAE Avignon) as both raw and boiled pieces for each variety, with approximately uniform

sizes, were stored at -80°C prior to grinding. They were initially broken into smaller pieces mechanically and then ground using an IKA grinder under liquid nitrogen.

Lyophilization

The samples were placed in plastic containers sealed with a layer of perforated parafilm. Lightly closed lids were positioned on top of the parafilm to allow water vapor to escape while preventing sample overflow. The containers were weighed before and after freeze-drying to determine the dry matter content of the samples.

Alcohol Insoluble Solid (AIS) extraction

To isolate cell walls, an ethanol-based extraction method (70 % ethanol) was used (Renard, 2005). This approach removes soluble compounds such as simple sugars, salts, minerals, vitamins, and pigments.

Five grams of freeze-dried and ground samples were mixed with 250 mL of boiling 70 % ethanol in a 400 mL beaker and stirred for 10 minutes. After cooling to room temperature, the suspension was agitated overnight at 4 °C. The mixture was centrifuged (9000 rpm, 15 °C, 7 min), and the pellet containing the cell walls was collected.

The cell walls were washed repeatedly with 70 % ethanol to remove all sugars, verified by the phenol-sulfuric test (DuBois et al., 1956). The cell walls were further washed with acetone (60 %, 80 %, and 100 %), dried at 35 °C for 48 hours, and weighed to quantify the AIS extraction yield.

Starch Removal from AIS (de-starching)

To analyze the cell wall polysaccharides in AIS from cassava, starch was removed via enzymatic hydrolysis targeting specifically this polysaccharide.

Eight grams of AIS were mixed with 200 mL of ultrapure water in a 400 mL Erlenmeyer flask and stirred at room temperature for 1 hour. Then, 3.2 mL of thermostable α -amylase was added, followed by sequential water bath treatments at 95 °C for 12 minutes and 70 °C for 30 minutes. After cooling, 25 mL of acetate buffer (pH 4.5) was added, and the suspension was incubated at 50 °C for 10 minutes.

Hydrolysis continued with the addition of 1.92 mL of amyloglucosidase, followed by stirring for 3 hours at 50 °C. The pH was adjusted to 7 using 1 M NaOH, and 3.2 mL of Subtilisin A was added before incubation at 35 °C for 1 hour. The reaction was stopped by adding 480 mL of 96% ethanol, and the solution was stirred overnight at 4 °C. The destarched AIS composed of cell wall polysaccharides, was recovered following the general AIS extraction protocol.

2.2.2 Mid-infrared spectroscopy Mid-IR

To evaluate the potential of mid-infrared (MID-IR) spectroscopy for predicting the quality parameters of cassava, and to explore correlations between this rapid and non-destructive method and traditional analytical techniques, MID-IR spectra were recorded at room temperature using Tensor 27 FTIR spectrometer (Bruker Optics, Wissembourg, France) was equipped with a single-reflectance horizontal ATR cell (Golden Gate equipped with a diamond crystal, Bruker Optics). The freeze-dried homogenized samples of apples were placed at the surface of the diamond crystal and were pressed with a system press tip flap. The samples were scanned at wavenumbers ranging from 4000 to 600 cm^{-1} and corrected against the background spectrum of air. The spectrum of each sample was obtained by taking the average of 24 scans. Each sample spectrum was obtained as the average of 24 scans. The crystal was cleaned with deionized water and dried with lint-free tissue between measurements to ensure accuracy. Instrument control and data acquisition were conducted using OPUS software (version 8.1, Bruker, France), supplied by the manufacturer.

This approach aims to provide a fast and reliable method for cassava quality analysis while reducing reliance on time-consuming laboratory techniques.

2.2.3 Starch Quantification

In boiled AIS material (AIS)

Starch content was determined using the Total Starch K-TSTA kit from Megazyme (Wicklow, Ireland). Two heating blocks were preheated to 50 °C and 100 °C. In triplicate, approximately 20 mg of starch-containing AIS (or de-starched material) were placed in screw-cap tubes, with one blank tube for each sample.

To each tube, 40 µL of α-amylase solution and 1.16 mL of acetate buffer (pH 5) were added. The tubes were vortexed and incubated at 100 °C for 20 minutes (vortexing every 5 minutes), followed by incubation at 50 °C for 10 minutes. Then, 40 µL of amyloglucosidase was added, and the tubes were incubated at 50 °C for 30 minutes. After cooling for 10 minutes and centrifugation (10 minutes at 5000 rpm, 15 °C), the supernatant was collected. A 1:30 dilution of the supernatant was prepared for starch quantification.

Starch quantification was performed using a microplate reader with a glucose standard curve. For each sample, 8 µL was pipetted in triplicate into a microplate, followed by 240 µL of GOPOD reagent (glucose oxidase-peroxidase). After mixing, the plate was incubated at 50 °C for 20 minutes, and absorbance was measured at 510 nm.

In raw AIS material (AIS)

Starch was analyzed in raw AIS material using the same protocol as for boiled AIS material. However, an additional step was included at the beginning for raw AIS: a **20-minute cooking step in 2 mL of pure water** to gelatinize the starch and enhance its accessibility to enzymes.

In the de-starched AIS material (de-AIS)

Starch content determination for resistant starch was performed using the Total Starch K-TSTA kit (Megazyme, Wicklow, Ireland). Two heating blocks were preheated to 50 °C and 100 °C. In triplicate, approximately 10 mg of de-starched AIS material were weighed into screw-cap tubes, with one blank tube prepared for each sample.

To each tube, 20 µL of 80% methanol and 200 µL of DMSO were added. The tubes were vortexed thoroughly and incubated at 100 °C for 6 minutes, with vortexing every 2 minutes to ensure proper mixing. Following this, 600 µL of diluted α-amylase solution (30-fold dilution in DMSO, pH 7) was added to each tube. The mixture was incubated at 100 °C for 20 minutes, with vortexing every 5 minutes, followed by an additional incubation at 50 °C for 10 minutes.

Next, 600 µL of sodium acetate buffer (pH 4.5) was added, followed by 20 µL of amyloglucosidase (AMG). The tubes were incubated at 50 °C for 30 minutes under gentle agitation. After cooling for 10 minutes at room temperature, the samples were centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 10 minutes at 15 °C. The supernatant was collected carefully for analysis.

Starch quantification was performed using a microplate reader and a glucose standard curve. For each sample, 8 µL of supernatant was pipetted in triplicate into a microplate, followed by 240 µL of GOPOD reagent (glucose oxidase-peroxidase). The plate was mixed gently and incubated at 50 °C for 20 minutes. Finally, the absorbance was measured at 510 nm, and the starch content was calculated based on the glucose standard curve.

2.2.4 Cell Wall Characterization

In order to determine cellulosic glucose, neutral sugars, included non glucosidic and cellulosic glucose, were analysed as alditol acetates after acid hydrolysis with two options: a simple hydrolysis for pectins and hemicelluloses, and a double hydrolysis for cellulose.

The double hydrolysis involved weighing 10 mg of de-starched AIS material and adding 250 μL of 72% sulfuric acid, followed by incubation at room temperature for 1 hour with vortexing every 15 minutes. Then, a solution of inositol (1 mg/mL) and ultrapure water were added, and the sample was incubated at 100°C for 3 hours. The simple hydrolysis was performed by weighing 10 mg of de-starched AIS material, adding a solution of inositol and 2 M sulfuric acid, and incubating at 100°C for 3 hours (Saeman et al., 1954).

After hydrolysis, the neutral sugars were made volatile by a two-step derivatization: reduction to alditols followed by acetylation. The reduction was carried out with 3 M NaBH_4 and 35% NH_4OH , followed by acetylation with N-methyl-imidazole and acetic anhydride. Finally, the alditols were extracted into an organic phase (dichloromethane), purified, and analyzed by GC-FID. (Englyst et al., 1982)

Tableau 3: Parameters for Alditol Acetates Analysis by GC-FID

Injection technique	Split (ratio 1/8)
Injection volume	1.5 μL
Carrier gas	H_2 (1.5 mL/min)
Capillary column	30 m x 0.25 mm ID, 0.25 μm film (Macherey-Nagel, Düren, Germany)
Temperature program	230°C (20 min)
Detector	FID (250°C, H_2 and compressed air)

2.2.5 Galacturonic acid quantification

The galacturonic acid assay was performed on the solutions obtained after the double hydrolysis of polysaccharides. These solutions were diluted 20 times, and 0.5 mL of each diluted solution was transferred into three test tubes, one of which was used for the blank. Then, 3 mL of a 0.0125 M sodium tetraborate solution was added to each tube. After mixing, the tubes were placed in a thermostatic bath at 80 °C for 10 minutes. The reaction was stopped by placing the tubes in an ice water bath until they reached ambient temperature. Finally, 50 μL of MHDP was added to the samples, and for the blanks, 50 μL of ultrapure water was added. A galacturonic acid standard curve, with concentrations ranging from 0 to 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, was prepared under the same conditions. After 10 minutes of incubation, the absorbance of the samples was measured at 520 nm using a spectrophotometer (Levigne et al., 2002) and (Renard & Ginies., 2009).

2.2.6 Methylation degree of pectin

This quantification was based on a saponification reaction. In 20 mL vials, 10 mg of samples were weighed. Next, 0.4 mL of CD_3OH (used as an internal standard), 3.8 mL of ultrapure water, and 0.8 mL of 1 M KOH were added. The vials were tightly sealed, vortexed, and the samples were injected into the GC-MS system after one hour. The analysis was performed using the headspace method.

The calibration curve was prepared using 0.4 mL of CD_3OH and 0.8 mL of KOH. Methanol was added to the solution in varying amounts (0.1 mL to 1 mL). Ultrapure water was then added to bring the total solution volume in the vial to 5 mL (Renard & Ginies., 2009).

Tableau 4: Methanol Quantification Parameters by GC/MS

Syringe temperature	60°C
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Injection technique	Split (ratio 1/15)
Injected volume	500 μ L
Injection temperature	220°C
Carrier gas	Helium (velocity of 45 cm/s)
Capillary column	UBWAX 30 m x 0.25 mm x 0.5 μ m
Program temperature	40°C
Interface temperature	230°C
Ion source	Electron ionization
Analyzer	Single quadrupole mass spectrometer
Detector	Secondary electron multiplier with conversion diode
Scans	5 scans/s

The degree of methylation (MD) was calculated using the following equation:

$$MD = 100 \times \frac{\text{MeOH}}{GA}$$

MeOH: Methanol (μ mol/mg) in de-starched AIS material

GA: Galacturonic acid (μ mol/mg) in de-starched AIS material

2.2.7 Significance of the Ratios Used for Pectin Characterization

Three key structural ratios were used to better understand the composition and functional properties of pectins: Gal A/Rha (galacturonic acid/rhamnose), (Ara + Gal)/Rha (arabinose + galactose/rhamnose), and Ara/Gal (arabinose/galactose). The Gal A/Rha ratio reflects the relative abundance of galacturonic acid, a major component of the homogalacturonan (HG) backbone, compared to rhamnose, a key element of the branched regions of rhamnogalacturonan (RG). A higher ratio indicates a predominance of homogalacturonan, which is associated with gelling properties and improved stability in food products, while a lower ratio suggests a more branched structure. The (Ara + Gal)/Rha ratio evaluates the combined content of arabinose and galactose relative to rhamnose, providing insights into the complexity and degree of branching in the pectin structure. A higher value indicates a highly branched pectin, enhancing gel-forming ability and texture modification. Lastly, the Ara/Gal ratio highlights the relative amounts of arabinose and galactose, revealing the nature of the pectin side chains present. A higher ratio suggests a greater presence of arabinans, which influence solubility and gelling properties. These ratios serve as essential indicators for linking the structural diversity of pectins to their functional applications as gelling, thickening, or stabilizing agents in food matrices.

2.2.1 Lignins quantification

Approximately 18 mg of non-de-starched AIS (alcohol-insoluble solids) material was weighed in duplicate. To each sample, 1 mL of Reagent 1 (containing 25% acetyl bromide, 72% glacial acetic acid, and 3% perchloric acid) was added to remove interfering phenolic materials. The mixture was vortexed thoroughly and heated at 70 °C for 30 minutes to dissolve the lignins.

After heating, 10 μL of the solution was transferred to a screw-cap tube, to which 570 μL of Reagent 2 (composed of 17.24% 2M NaOH and 82.76% glacial acetic acid) and 20 μL of hydroxylamine (0.52 g/mL) were added. The mixture was vortexed again, and the volume was adjusted to 2 mL with glacial acetic acid.

Finally, the absorbance at 280 nm was measured, and the lignins content was calculated using a standard lignins calibration curve ([Morrison, 1972](#)).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The figures below present the histograms of the mean starch content (%) in the de-starched AIS material, as well as the residual starch after de-starching, accompanied by the standard error.

Tableau 5: Yields on a dry matter basis (%) and neutral sugars, galacturonic acid and methanol composition(mg/g AIS) of AIS in Cassava varieties

Varieties	Process	Non-de-starched AIS		De-starched AIS material (mg/g)										MD (%)
		Starch (%)	Lignins (mg/g)	SR mg/g	Rha	Fuc	Ara	Xyl	Man	Gal	Total Glc	MeOH	GalA	
COL1516	Raw	68,08 ± 1,39	126,39 ± 1,83	39,57 ± 1,63	4,57 ± 0,23	1,55 ± 0,16	15,1 ± 0,6	13,39 ± 0,94	10,32 ± 2,4	67,61 ± 2,36	98,21 ± 5,93	8,57 ± 0,21	100,71 ± 6,11	47,71 ± 3,03
COL1516	Boiled	77,33 ± 1,38	55,56 ± 0,67	25,23 ± 0,27	7,43 ± 0,35	2,97 ± 0,18	21,29 ± 1,07	27,25 ± 0,55	18,18 ± 0,6	117,82 ± 4,1	158,88 ± 6,58	3,68 ± 0,22	66,12 ± 4,02	31,24 ± 2,16
CR63R	Raw	66,04 ± 2,25	112,7 ± 6,21	54,69 ± 1,87	7,24 ± 0,25	2,45 ± 0,05	16,51 ± 1,37	32,1 ± 4,64	13,87 ± 0,18	76,29 ± 3,65	147,01 ± 8,97	6,13 ± 0	110,96 ± 5,15	30,73 ± 1,42
CR63B	Boiled	81,08 ± 3,01	61,07 ± 2,85	43,94 ± 1,39	7,12 ± 0,23	2,3 ± 0,09	16,7 ± 0,69	21,88 ± 0,22	23,51 ± 0,13	99,22 ± 1,2	174,77 ± 5,52	2,68 ± 0	54,57 ± 6,29	28,39 ± 2,95
HMC1R	Raw	76,31 ± 1,53	116,7 ± 7,8	47,14 ± 1,68	6,09 ± 0,11	2,4 ± 0,03	21,62 ± 1,09	26,64 ± 2,66	12,26 ± 1,37	80,83 ± 2,35	139,68 ± 11,42	9,03 ± 0,4	96,39 ± 9,3	54,26 ± 5,8
HMC1B	Boiled	80,28 ± 1,57	216,76 ± 6,15	43,65 ± 0,94	7,21 ± 0,17	2,3 ± 0,23	22,93 ± 0,63	34,69 ± 2,08	19,48 ± 1,25	93,67 ± 3,4	194,31 ± 16,4	3,69 ± 0,15	71,05 ± 3,97	29,06 ± 1,81
IND135R	Raw	71,47 ± 0,65	85,39 ± 0,36	32,13 ± 1,36	6,58 ± 0,51	2,05 ± 0,23	15,85 ± 1,55	23,89 ± 1,19	15,61 ± 1,8	83,17 ± 7,02	155,19 ± 8,5	8,04 ± 0,01	82,93 ± 8,36	56,05 ± 5,45
IND135B	Boiled	76,37 ± 4,98	48,37 ± 0,16	39,25 ± 0,78	6,73 ± 0,52	2,93 ± 0,25	16,27 ± 0,37	29,73 ± 1,17	22,23 ± 1,57	114,84 ± 2,41	164,55 ± 9,81	2,4 ± 0,06	43,17 ± 4,97	32,49 ± 3,3
COL2215R	Raw	70,55 ± 0,65	76,48 ± 1,74	40,29 ± 1,68	6,26 ± 0,49	1,97 ± 0,34	18,23 ± 0,69	23,13 ± 1,29	16,45 ± 0,26	85,6 ± 4,62	194,93 ± 8,54	8,05 ± 0,02	100,61 ± 2,52	44,14 ± 1,05
COL2215B	Boiled	69,66 ± 1,26	37,46 ± 2,16	42,85 ± 0,57	8,1 ± 0,17	3,3 ± 0,08	22,19 ± 0,12	29,02 ± 0,85	24,92 ± 0,61	109,4 ± 0,71	206,14 ± 7,66	5,42 ± 0,23	91,17 ± 3,4	32,96 ± 1,29
PER183R	Raw	70,19 ± 0,66	65,38 ± 2,33	38,91 ± 1,83	6,51 ± 0,18	1,89 ± 0,03	14,74 ± 0,02	27,73 ± 0,76	15,03 ± 0,72	68,42 ± 2,56	193,33 ± 4,56	8,04 ± 0,42	101,65 ± 8,31	44,94 ± 3,51
PER183B	Boiled	66,74 ± 1,89	223,25 ± 9,95	86,47 ± 1,09	10,01 ± 0,35	3,55 ± 0,02	19,38 ± 0,33	35,48 ± 0,38	26,33 ± 1,02	109,86 ± 1,32	246,55 ± 4,66	6,31 ± 0,06	95,32 ± 4,21	36,74 ± 1,6
COL1505R	Raw	76,87 ± 1,32	89,61 ± 0,33	38,14 ± 0,87	5,77 ± 0,4	1,65 ± 0,12	17,5 ± 0,27	24,85 ± 0,78	15,16 ± 0,53	86,64 ± 1,6	195,4 ± 2,98	7,15 ± 0,06	100,33 ± 6,7	40,03 ± 2,5
COL1505B	Boiled	85,87 ± 1,68	207,22 ± 13,26	41,43 ± 1,57	9,32 ± 0,3	3,73 ± 0,12	24,19 ± 0,69	34,37 ± 2,48	28,09 ± 1,36	123,9 ± 2,63	242,06 ± 26,67	5,59 ± 0,17	82,15 ± 1,77	37,5 ± 0,79
SM11278R	Raw	73,15 ± 1,83	138,42 ± 3,53	40,94 ± 0,75	6,25 ± 0,3	2,06 ± 0,11	21,01 ± 0,6	25,45 ± 1,44	16,98 ± 0,19	92,73 ± 4,9	220,96 ± 13,89	6,94 ± 0,13	80,38 ± 4,8	48,41 ± 3,14
SM11278B	Boiled	75,32 ± 1,7	48,21 ± 0,79	41,04 ± 0,73	8,8 ± 0,29	3,96 ± 0,12	25,2 ± 0,68	26,75 ± 0,53	26,46 ± 0,27	113,04 ± 1,89	214,3 ± 7,67	4,56 ± 0,12	77,63 ± 2,82	32,53 ± 1,11

DM: Dry Matter, AIS: Alcohol Insoluble Solid, SR: Starch Residue, Rha: Rhamnose, Fuc: Fucose, Ara: Arabinose, Gal: Galactose, Glu: Glucose, MeOH: Methanol, GalA: Galacturonic Acid, NSP: Non-Starch Polysaccharides, MD: Methylation Degree.

3.1 Yields

3.1.1 Dry matter yield

The eight cassava varieties analyzed exhibit varying dry matter percentages (Ydm) in their raw state, ranging from 31% for PER183 to 43% for COL2215. After cooking, the dry matter content is consistently lower than in the raw samples. This decrease is attributed to water absorption during cooking, which increases the total sample weight. Following lyophilization, which removes the absorbed water, a lower proportion of dry matter is observed in the cooked samples, which indicated that some material leaches out of the pieces of cassava during boiling. These results for raw varieties are comparable to the range of 37.82%–39.64% reported by (Koko et al., 2014).

Overall, no significant variation is observed between the varieties. However, the AIS yield (Y AIS) is consistently slightly higher in boiled samples compared to raw ones. This is likely due to the removal of soluble compounds, including pectins, during the boiling process, which leads to a relative concentration of the insoluble fraction.

The de-starching yield (Ydes) varies among cassava varieties, reflecting differences in their response to the de-starching process. The varieties **COL1516**, **CR63**, **HMC1**, and **IND135** exhibit higher yields in the raw state compared to after cooking (i.e. more starch is lost during boiling, and/or more starch can be removed after boiling). Conversely, the varieties **COL2215**, **PER183**, and **SM127-8** show higher yields after cooking (i.e. more non-starch compounds are lost during boiling, resulting in a relative concentration of starch in the boiled samples) [difference maybe not statistically significant]. The variety **COL1505** presents similar yields before and after cooking.

Figure 1: Dry matter yield, non-de-starched AIS material extraction yield, and de-starching yield expressed as percentages.

3.2 Starch Quantification

Among the eight studied cassava varieties, the starch content in the non-de starched AIS material ranges from 66% to 77% in raw varieties and from 67% to 86% in boiled varieties (figure 2). A significant difference was observed between the varieties before and after cooking. The results indicate a higher starch content in cooked samples, likely due to the leaching of other compounds, such as pectins, into the cooking water, which increases the starch-to-non-de starched AIS ratio. Since starch cannot be generated during cooking, this shift reflects a redistribution of the remaining components.

Notably, the PER183 variety exhibited a unique trend, with higher starch content before cooking, suggesting minimal leaching of compounds during the process. Similarly, the COL2215 variety showed a less pronounced change in starch content before and after cooking. These findings suggest that whereas starch is retained during cooking, the ratio is influenced by the loss of other compounds.

For comparison, starch content has been reported to range from 63% to 83% on a dry weight basis in white cassava and from 55% to 76% in yellow cassava (Anggraini et al., 2009). Other studies report values ranging from 60% to 87% for cassava starch (Onitilo et al., 2007).

The starch removal procedure significantly reduced the starch content; however, residual starch was still detected in the de-starched AIS material. Residual starch levels ranged from 2.5% in the raw COL1516 variety to 5.5% in the raw COL2215 variety. For cooked samples, residual starch levels varied from 3.9% in the cooked COL2215 variety to 8.7% in the cooked CR63 variety, with the highest residual starch percentage observed in the cooked CR63 variety. These results highlight the efficiency of the de-starching process while acknowledging its limitations in completely removing starch for certain varieties. No consistent general trend was observed regarding the behavior of the varieties in response to de-starching before and after cooking. However, the COL1516, CR63, and PER183 varieties tended to retain significantly more starch in the cooked state than in the raw state. In contrast, the HMC1 and COL2215 varieties exhibited the opposite trend, with lower residual starch content after cooking. Meanwhile, the IND135, COL1505, and SM127-8 varieties showed no significant differences in residual starch content between the raw and cooked states.

Figure 2: Starch percentage in AIS non-de-starched material of cassava varieties.

Figure 3: Starch percentage in de-starched AIS material of cassava varieties.

3.3 Lignins (non-destarched AIS) and Non-Starch Polysaccharides Quantification (destarched AIS).

The analysis of lignin content in different cassava varieties, comparing raw and cooked states, revealed significant variations between varieties and processing conditions. In the raw state, lignin content ranged from 65 mg/g AIS in PER183R to 138 mg/g AIS in SM1127-8R. After cooking, values ranged from 37 mg/g in COL2215B to 223 mg/g in PER183B (Figure 4).

The PER183 variety stands out, with a notably low lignin content before cooking (65 mg/g), but a sharp increase to 223 mg/g afterward. This rise may be due to the relative concentration of lignin as soluble compounds leached into the cooking water. HMC1 (117 mg/g raw, 217 mg/g cooked) and COL1505 (90 mg/g raw, 207 mg/g cooked) showed a similar behavior. In contrast, COL1516 (126 mg/g raw, 56 mg/g cooked), CR63 (113 mg/g raw, 61 mg/g cooked), IND135 (85 mg/g raw, 48 mg/g cooked), COL2215 (76 mg/g raw, 37 mg/g cooked) and SM1127-8 (138 mg/g raw, 48 mg/g cooked) show a decrease in lignin content after cooking, suggesting partial solubilization or thermal degradation of lignin. These results highlight the importance of cell wall composition and the interactions between lignin, hemicelluloses, and cellulose in determining lignin retention during cooking.

Further research could explore lignin behavior in starch-depleted materials (de-starched AIS), complementing the current analysis of non-de-starched AIS. Additionally, measuring soluble compounds in the cooking water, investigating lignin interactions with other cell wall components, and conducting thermogravimetric and spectroscopic analyses could provide deeper insights into these transformations.

NSP Analysis:

The analysis of Non-Starch Polysaccharides (NSP) reveals a significant post-cooking increase in all cassava varieties analyzed (Figure 5). This trend can be explained by the loss of soluble compounds, particularly pectins, into the cooking water, resulting in the relative concentration of insoluble fractions, including NSP.

Among the varieties studied, COL1505 exhibits the highest NSP content after cooking (548 mg/g), followed closely by PER183 (546 mg/g), indicating strong thermal stability of NSP in these varieties. In contrast, IND135 and CR63 show the lowest increases, from respectively 386 and 356 mg/g raw to 400 mg/g cooked, suggesting a lower proportion of soluble compounds or reduced NSP thermal stability.

Overall, the notable NSP increases in COL1505 and PER183 may be attributed to more cross-linked, resistant structures interacting with lignin or cellulose. Conversely, the more modest NSP increases observed in CR63, IND135, and HMC1 could result from partial thermal degradation or greater solubilization of NSP into the cooking medium. These findings underscore the structural differences in NSP across cassava varieties, influencing their behavior during cooking.

Figure 4: Comparison of lignins composition in cassava varieties (in non-destarched AIS) before and after cooking.

Figure 5: Comparison of non-starch polysaccharides (NSP) composition in cassava varieties (in destarched AIS) before and after cooking.

3.4 Cell wall composition

Galacturonic acid (GalA), methanol (MeOH), and DM decreased significantly after cooking for all cassava varieties. With different trend depending on varieties. Hence, varieties COL1516, CR63, HMC1, and IND135 tended to lose more GalA after cooking compared to COL2215, PER183, and SM11278.

The decrease of both GalA content and degree of methylation could be due to the activities of pectin methylesterases, and polygalacturonase during cooking which led to both deduction of DM and pectin solubilisation.

Additionally, the reduction in the degree of methylation of pectins modifies their properties. This reduction may influence pectin solubility and their interactions with other components, potentially affecting the structure of cell walls and the textural properties of cassava after cooking.

Moreover, arabinose, mannose, galactose, xylose (except in CR63), glucose (except in SM11278), and rhamnose (except in CR63) cell wall contents tended to decrease after cooking certainly due to chemical modification.

For instance, varieties such as CR63 and IND135 showed greater reductions in GalA, suggesting a higher solubility of homogalacturonans or a weaker pectin network that disintegrates more readily in the cooking process. In contrast, varieties like PER183 and SM11278 exhibit a more moderate decline, possibly due to structural reinforcement by other cell wall components, such as hemicelluloses or lignins, that stabilize pectic domains.

The observed decrease in neutral sugars (arabinose, mannose, galactose, and xylose) further suggests that non-starch polysaccharides (NSPs) undergo compositional shifts, influencing the mechanical and textural properties of cassava. These reductions could be due to chemical modification or partial solubilization of hemicelluloses and rhamnogalacturonans, which could contribute to the softening and loss of structural integrity in certain cassava varieties.

These results strengthen the hypothesis that pectin modifications play a role in the texture of cassava after cooking. The observed reductions in the degree of methylation (DM) indicate a progressive demethylation of pectins, which could lead to: Increase in pectin solubility, promoting softening in varieties with low lignins and hemicellulose reinforcement. A greater interaction between pectins and divalent cations (for example, calcium), which can influence gelling properties and firmness in varieties that retain higher levels of GalA. Moreover, the increase in lignins concentration in certain varieties after cooking suggests that the insoluble fraction becomes relatively enriched as the soluble compounds dissolve in the cooking water. This effect could explain why some varieties maintain greater resistance to decomposition, while others become crumblier and mealier.

Figure 6: Composition of cell wall in cassava varieties (mg/g) in de-starched AIS material and methylation degree.

3.5 Polysaccharide Ratios and Their Impact on Cassava Texture After Cooking

The cooking process induces structural modifications in cassava polysaccharides, influencing directly the texture of different varieties. By examining polysaccharide ratios before and after cooking, we can better understand how these transformations affect cell wall cohesion and firmness.

The **Ara/Xyl (Arabinose/Xylose)** ratio reflects the proportion of arabinose relative to xylose in hemicelluloses and pectins. A decrease in this ratio after cooking, as observed for **COL1516** and **IND135**, suggests **solubilization of arabinans, leading to a loss of water retention and a firmer texture. Conversely, some varieties, such as PER183**, exhibit an increase in this ratio, possibly indicating a relative concentration of arabinose due to the loss of other soluble polysaccharides. This variation influences the malleability of cassava roots after cooking.

The **Xyl/Man (Xylose/Mannose)** ratio remains relatively stable in most varieties, indicating that hemicellulose structures undergo minimal modifications during cooking. However, some varieties, such as **CR63**, show a significant decrease in this ratio, suggesting selective degradation of xylose-rich hemicelluloses. This may result in a loss of structural cohesion, leading to a more friable and less resistant texture.

The **Man/Glu (Mannose/ total Glucose)** ratio reflects the relative stability of mannose and glucose within polysaccharides. Most varieties show little variation, suggesting that these components remain relatively stable during cooking. However, some varieties, such as **CR63**, exhibit a marked increase in this ratio, indicating a possible selective loss of glucose. This phenomenon may be associated with cell wall disorganization, leading to a weaker texture.

The **(Ara+Gal)/Rha (Arabinose + Galactose / Rhamnose)** ratio is a key indicator of pectin branching. An increase in this ratio after cooking, as observed for **IND135**, suggests a higher concentration of branched polysaccharides due to the solubilization of rhamnose-rich fractions. This change may enhance gelling ability and water retention, contributing to a more adhesive and moist texture. Conversely, a decrease in this ratio, as seen in **COL2215**, suggests solubilization of arabinans and galactans, potentially resulting in a less cohesive texture.

The **GalA/Rha (Galacturonic Acid / Rhamnose)** ratio serves as a marker of homogalacturonan content in pectins. A general decrease in this ratio after cooking, as observed for **IND135**, suggests a significant loss of soluble homogalacturonans, leading to a reduction in cell wall rigidity. This loss may contribute to a stickier and more malleable texture.

The **Gal/Ara (Galactose/Arabinose)** ratio helps to evaluate the nature of pectin side chains. Most varieties show an increase after cooking, as seen in **IND135**, which could indicate a high concentration of galactose. This transformation may contribute to a more cohesive and less friable texture.

The **GalA/(Rha+Ara+Gal)** ratio measures the proportion of galacturonic acid relative to total pectin sugars. A marked decrease after cooking in all varieties suggests extensive pectin solubilization, altering cell wall cohesion and structure. This reduction may explain a less firm and more malleable texture.

Overall, the analysis of polysaccharide ratios highlights structural transformations induced by cooking. Homogalacturonans and xylose-rich hemicelluloses appear to be particularly affected, leading to changes in cell wall cohesion. Varieties with high arabinan and galactan retention, such as **PER183** and **COL1505**, maintain a better gelling capacity, resulting in a smoother and more cohesive texture. Conversely, varieties with significant pectin solubilization, such as **CR63** and **IND135**, develop a friable and less adhesive texture.

These findings provide essential insights into cassava cell wall transformation during cooking, which could be leveraged to optimize varietal selection based on consumer preferences and industrial applications.

Tableau 6: Ratios of polysaccharides

Variétés	Hemicelluloses			Pectins		
	Ara/Xyl	Xyl/Man	Man/Glu	GalA/Rha	Gal/Ara	GalA/(Rha+Ara+Gal)
COL1516R	1,13	1,59	0,14	20,53	3,65	1,02
COL1516B	0,78	1,84	0,16	8,71	4,51	0,42
CR63R	0,51	2,84	0,14	14,27	3,77	0,98
CR63B	0,76	1,14	0,30	6,44	4,84	0,36
HMC1R	0,81	2,67	0,14	14,77	3,05	0,78
HMC1B	0,66	2,19	0,13	9,18	3,33	0,51
IND135R	0,66	1,88	0,15	10,19	4,28	0,61
IND135B	0,55	1,64	0,19	4,94	5,75	0,23
COL2215R	0,79	1,73	0,12	14,97	3,83	0,81
COL2215B	0,55	1,65	0,13	8,49	4,62	0,58
PER183R	0,53	2,26	0,10	14,18	3,78	0,98
PER183B	0,70	1,50	0,14	9,53	4,17	0,54
COL1505R	0,70	2,01	0,10	11,64	4,03	0,58
COL1505B	0,94	1,24	0,16	8,70	3,66	0,50
SM11278R	0,83	1,84	0,10	13,08	3,60	0,65
SM11278B	0,76	1,43	0,16	8,93	4,02	0,49

3.6 Principal Component Analysis and Correlation Insights: Exploring Variable Interactions in Cassava Composition.

3.6.1 PCA for physicochemical results

The results of the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) indicate that, based on the physicochemical data, it is possible to distinguish between raw and cooked cassava varieties along the first axis, which explains 45.1% of the total variance. The raw varieties tend to cluster together and are primarily characterized by their higher levels of galacturonic acid, methanol, and a higher degree of methylation.

After cooking, the cassava varieties exhibit greater dispersion, reflecting their differentiated responses to the cooking process. They are more associated with higher levels of neutral sugars from the cell walls. This relative increase could be attributed to the significant loss of galacturonic acid and methanol during cooking in water, which increases the ratio of neutral sugars to other components. These changes, particularly the loss of methanol, directly affect the degree of methylation (DM) of the cooked varieties.

The second PCA axis, which explains 16.1% of the variance, differentiates between the cooked varieties. For instance, the PER183 variety is distinguished by its high lignin content and reduced levels of starch and residual starch after cooking. Conversely, the CR63 variety is primarily characterized by its higher starch content compared to other varieties and its lower lignin content.

Figure 7: PCA of physicochemical results.

3.6.2 PCA of physicochemical data and sensorial texture, applicable only to cooked samples.

According to the results of the sensory analyses, the varieties COL1516, CR63, IND135, and COL1505 are characterized by their adhesiveness, mealiness, and friability. Similarly, the varieties PER183 and SM1127 exhibit pronounced mealiness and adhesiveness.

In contrast, the variety HMC1 is primarily defined by its hardness and moisture content. Additionally, HMC1 distinguishes itself from other varieties by its higher degree of glassy appearance, a unique sensory attribute.

The variety COL2215 shares characteristics such as adhesiveness, mealiness, and friability with some other varieties but is also notable for its pronounced hardness.

Figure 8: The sensorial profile for cassava varieties.

The joint representation of physicochemical and sensory results in the PCA reveals that the variety HMC1 stands out from the others due to its sensory characteristics, including moisture, hardness, and glassy aspect. These attributes positively correlate with its high lignins and xylose content, reinforcing the structural role of cell wall components in shaping texture.

Lignins, a rigid polymer in cell walls, contributes to cell stiffness and reduced degradation, explaining both the hardness and glassy appearance of HMC1. Additionally, its high lignins content may play a role in moisture retention, potentially influencing its perceived texture. Meanwhile, xylose, a key component of hemicelluloses, interacts with cellulose microfibrils and lignins, forming a reinforced structural network. These interactions enhance the mechanical properties of the cell wall, further impacting the sensory perception of hardness and moisture retention.

While pectins (represented by galacturonic acid, the major component of pectins) are known to play a key role in determining texture, the sensory analysis alone did not clearly reveal a direct correlation between pectins and the perceived texture of cassava varieties. This suggests that the influence of pectins on texture may be more complex and could require alternative analytical approaches to be fully characterized.

The sensory variables adhesiveness, friability, and mealiness are negatively correlated with the glassy aspect, hardness, and moisture content, reinforcing the distinct textural profiles observed among the varieties.

Principal Component 1 (explaining 40.2% of the variance) allows for the distinction of the varieties Col1516, CR63, and IND135 based on their mealiness, adhesiveness, and friability characteristics. These varieties group together due to their specific sensory texture, highlighting significant differences in the perception of cassava texture across the studied samples.

Figure 9: PCA of physicochemical and sensorial texture results.

3.6.1 PCA of physicochemical data and mechanical texture, applicable only for 5 varieties.

For the evaluation of mechanical texture, results were collected for only five cassava varieties due to the insufficient availability of samples for the remaining three. Despite this limitation, the observed trends allow for meaningful interpretations.

The HMC1 variety stands out from the others based on several mechanical texture characteristics, including CP+F (Count Peaks+ F), Ldist (Linear Distance F-T 1:4), CP-F (Count Peaks- F), Area.F (Surface F-T 1:4), MaxF (Maximum Force), and GFT (Gradient F-T 1:2). These parameters are negatively correlated with D.MaxF (Distance at Maximum Force), galactose, and residual starch after de-starching (Starch residue).

By integrating mechanical texture data with physicochemical composition, a positive correlation was observed between galactose and the mechanical texture parameter D.MaxF. Since galactose is a key component of pectins rather than hemicelluloses, this finding suggests a potential link between pectin structure and mechanical properties, a relationship that is not clearly detected through sensory texture analysis alone.

Furthermore, the integration of physicochemical and mechanical texture data allowed for a better distinction of specific cassava varieties. The PER183 variety is characterized by higher levels of mannose, rhamnose, glucose, and galacturonic acid compared to other varieties. A positive correlation was also observed between the mechanical texture characteristic End.F (End Force at 20 mm) and lignins, xylose, and de-starching yield (Ydestrach).

Unlike the sensory texture results, mechanical texture analysis highlights the influence of starch content on structural properties. However, no direct correlation was found between starch quantity and mechanical resistance, suggesting that starch organization within the matrix may play a more crucial role than its absolute content.

Figure 10: PCA of physicochemical and mechanical texture results of 5 cassava varieties.

3.7 Mid-Infrared Spectroscopy (MID-IR) Analysis of Cassava Materials

3.7.1 Freeze-dried cassava powder, de-starched AIS material, and non-de-starched AIS material Mid-IR analysis.

Mid-infrared (MIR) spectra of freeze-dried cassava powder, de-starched AIS material, and non-de-starched AIS material.

Figure 11: Freeze-dried cassava powder, de-starched AIS material, and non-de-starched AIS material Mid-IR analysis.

The Mid-Infrared (MIR) spectroscopy analysis, performed on freeze-dried cassava powder (FDCP), de-starched AIS material, and non-de-starched AIS material, allowed us to differentiate these samples based on Principal Component 1 (PC1), which explains 80.2% of the variance.

The de-starched AIS material is clearly separated on the right side of the PCA graph, while the freeze-dried cassava powder (FDCP) and non-de-starched AIS material (ND AIS) form distinct clusters elsewhere. This separation aligns with previous physicochemical analyses, which highlighted differences in pectin content, starch levels, and hemicellulose composition between these cassava fractions.

- De-starched AIS material is mainly characterized by 997.5 cm^{-1} , which may correspond to C-O stretching vibrations of polysaccharides, particularly hemicelluloses (Liu et al., 2021). This confirms previous findings that hemicelluloses contribute significantly to the structural integrity of cassava cell walls, especially in starch-depleted fractions.
- Non-de-starched AIS material (ND AIS) is associated with 1648 cm^{-1} , which may correspond to C=O stretching vibrations of pectins and organic acids (Coates, 2000). This supports pectin's role in cassava texture, as also observed in previous biochemical analyses of galacturonic acid and methylation degree variations.
- Freeze-dried cassava powder (FDCP) is primarily characterized by 1057 cm^{-1} , seems to correspond to C-O vibrations of glycosides, indicating the presence of complex polysaccharides (Talari et al., 2017). This result aligns with the identified glycosidic bonds in starch and NSP analyses, confirming the role of cell wall carbohydrates in cassava composition.

Within the non-de-starched AIS material group, a clear distinction is observed between raw and boiled samples, consistent with previous findings on cooking-induced structural changes.

According to Principal Component 2 (PC2), which explains 7.4% of the variance, we observe:

- FDCP (Freeze-dried cassava powder), characterized by 1065 cm^{-1} and 1037 cm^{-1} , which seem to correspond to C-O vibrations of glycosidic bonds in starch (Liu et al., 2021; Talari et al., 2017). This reinforces earlier conclusions on starch structural modifications and its influence on cassava texture.
- Non-de-starched AIS material (Raw), associated with 3227 cm^{-1} , seems to be linked to O-H stretching vibrations of polysaccharides, particularly pectins (Talari et al., 2017). This reflects pectin's role in water retention, as previously discussed in hydration and texture analyses.
- Non-de-starched AIS material (Boiled), characterized by 1640 cm^{-1} , seems to be linked to C=O vibrations of methyl ester groups in pectins (Coates, 2000). This supports earlier findings that pectin de-methylation occurs post-cooking, leading to changes in gel-forming ability and cassava's textural properties.

3.7.2 Freeze-dried cassava powder Mid-IR analysis

Mid-infrared (MIR) spectra of freeze-dried cassava powder

Figure 12: Freeze-dried cassava powder Mid-IR analysis

The Mid-Infrared (MIR) spectroscopy analysis, conducted specifically on freeze-dried cassava powder (FDCP), successfully differentiated raw and boiled samples based on Principal Component 1 (PC1), which explains 47.8% of the variance.

The analysis separated to some extent the raw cassava varieties, characterized by 749.5 cm^{-1} , a region commonly associated with ring vibrations in polysaccharides, particularly pectins and hemicelluloses (Liu et al., 2021). This suggests that pectin and hemicellulose structures play a key role in the spectral differentiation of raw cassava samples.

The cooked cassava varieties are primarily distinguished by:

- 1051 cm^{-1} , seems to be linked to C-O stretching vibrations in glycosidic bonds of starch, indicating structural modifications due to gelatinization (Talari et al., 2017). This confirms previous observations on starch reorganization during cooking.
- 998 cm^{-1} , which may correspond to stretching vibrations of degraded pectin and hemicelluloses, suggesting thermal breakdown of cell wall components (Liu et al., 2021). This aligns with findings on pectin de-methylation and polysaccharide solubilization post-cooking.

However, Principal Component 2 (PC2), which explains a smaller portion of the variance, did not reveal significant differentiation between the samples, indicating that MIR spectroscopy primarily captures structural changes in major polysaccharides rather than subtle compositional variations.

3.7.3 Non de-starched AIS Material Mid-IR analysis

Figure 13: Non de-starched AIS Matrerial Mid-IR analysis.

The Mid-Infrared Spectroscopy (MID-IR) analysis, conducted on non-de-starched AIS material, separated cooked samples from raw samples.

This method also identified outlier boiled varieties, such as COL2215, PER183, and CR63. Despite the limited number of replicates, these results highlight the potential of MID-IR for efficiently differentiating cassava varieties and open new avenues for further research. Specifically, this technique could help establish correlations between MID-IR findings and traditional analytical methods, such as physicochemical composition, polysaccharide ratio analysis, and texture measurements.

The cooked samples (boiled), according to Principal Component 1 (PC1), which explains 57.3% of the variance, were characterized by:

- 992.3 cm^{-1} , which may correspond to C-O stretching vibrations in hemicelluloses and starch degradation products (Liu et al., 2021). This aligns with the observed starch reorganization and solubilization effects post-cooking.

Furthermore, Principal Component 2 (PC2), which explains 25% of the variance, enabled the differentiation of PER183 (boiled) and COL2215 (boiled), associated with:

- 970.8 cm^{-1} seems to be aligned with vibrations of esterified pectins or branched polysaccharides that influence adhesive properties (Liu et al., 2021). This correlates with previous findings that these varieties retain branched polysaccharides (Ara+Gal/Rha ratios), contributing to their adhesive and cohesive textures.

These results align with findings from PCA of physicochemical and sensory analyses, as well as polysaccharide ratios and mechanical texture tests. For instance:

- PER183 and COL2215 retained higher levels of branched polysaccharides, reinforcing their adhesive and cohesive textures.
- CR63 exhibited a higher starch content and lower pectin retention, explaining its increased friability.

- The shift in starch-related peaks (e.g., 992.3 cm^{-1}) confirms starch modifications, reinforcing findings from starch quantification and pectin solubilization studies.

This analysis demonstrates that MID-IR spectroscopy can effectively replicate key findings from traditional, time-intensive methods, while offering a rapid, non-destructive alternative for cassava quality assessment. However, further validation with a larger sample set is necessary to confirm the robustness of this technique across diverse cassava varieties and processing conditions.

3.7.4 De-starched AIS Material Mid-IR analysis

Figure 14: De-starched AIS Material Mid-IR analysis.

The Mid-Infrared Spectroscopy (MID-IR) analysis conducted on de-starched AIS material did not reveal significant differences between the cooked and raw cassava varieties. It is likely that the thermal de-starching process ($95\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 12 min, $70\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 30 min, $50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 10 min) disrupted cell wall integrity, altered pectin and hemicellulose organization, and reduced spectral differences between samples. Additionally, residual starch present in the de-starched AIS material could have further influenced the spectral signals, masking initial compositional variations.

While MID-IR failed to differentiate raw and cooked samples, traditional biochemical analyses still detected significant differences, likely due to their higher sensitivity in quantifying specific molecular changes in pectins, lignins, and neutral sugars. This suggests that MID-IR alone may not fully capture all structural modifications occurring during cassava processing.

Although de-starching is useful for isolating cell wall polysaccharides, analyzing non-de-starched samples may better preserve the natural matrix interactions that influence texture. Future studies should systematically compare both approaches to determine which method provides the most relevant insights into cassava quality traits and processing effects.

4 CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

This study highlights the key role of cell wall polysaccharides in the structural changes of cassava composition during cooking. **The interest of MID-IR spectroscopy lies in its ability to screen a large number of varieties and cooking conditions, thanks to its simplicity and rapid application directly on dry matter or MIA without any extraction.** This technique enabled the identification of major modifications in cell wall components, particularly the degradation of pectins and hemicelluloses, confirmed by the decrease in MID-IR signals associated with the C=O of pectins (1648 cm^{-1} , 1640 cm^{-1}) and the C-O of hemicelluloses (997 cm^{-1}) (Liu et al., 2021). Furthermore, starch reorganization was evidenced by changes in glycosidic bonds (1051 cm^{-1} , 1065 cm^{-1}), reflecting gelatinization and partial degradation of amyloid structures (Liu et al., 2021).

The impact of these transformations varies depending on the analyzed varieties. Lignins- and xylose-rich varieties, such as HMC1, maintain a firm texture, whereas PER183 and COL1505, which retain more branched polysaccharides, develop a more adhesive and mealy texture. In contrast, CR63 and IND135 exhibit a more friable structure, suggesting an increased solubilization of cell wall components. These observations confirm that starch quantity alone does not determine the final texture. Some varieties maintain a high starch content while remaining friable, whereas others exhibit better cohesion despite a lower starch content, highlighting the importance of starch-pectin interactions and the molecular structure of starch (Liu et al., 2021).

The integration of MID-IR spectroscopy with conventional cassava analysis methods opens promising perspectives. While MID-IR effectively captured key polysaccharide transformations, its inability to clearly differentiate de-starched samples underscores the need to combine it with biochemical and mechanical analyses for a more comprehensive understanding of cell wall interactions.

These results could be leveraged to optimize cassava processing methods, adjusting cooking parameters to preserve polysaccharides and ensure optimal textural quality. Additionally, this data can be utilized to refine varietal selection criteria within the RTBfoods project, incorporating post-cooking textural behavior in alignment with industry and consumer expectations.

Finally, combining MID-IR spectroscopy with other analytical techniques, such as Raman spectroscopy and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), would further deepen our understanding of polysaccharide and starch thermal transitions, enhancing the effectiveness of this approach in studying cassava transformations. This study highlights the importance of integrating spectral, biochemical, and textural analyses for a comprehensive characterization of cassava and the development of varieties better suited to agro-industrial requirements.

5 PARTNERS AND THEIR ROLES

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6 REFERENCES

- Anggraini, V., Sudarmonowati, E., Hartati, N.Sri., Suurs, L., Visser, R.G.F., 2009. Characterization of Cassava Starch Attributes of Different Genotypes. *Starch - Stärke* 61, 472–481. <https://doi.org/10.1002/star.200800121>
- Coates, J., 2000. Interpretation of Infrared Spectra, A Practical Approach, in: Meyers, R.A. (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of Analytical Chemistry*. Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470027318.a5606>
- DuBois, Michel., Gilles, K.A., Hamilton, J.K., Rebers, P.A., Smith, Fred., 1956. Colorimetric Method for Determination of Sugars and Related Substances. *Anal. Chem.* 28, 350–356. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac60111a017>
- Englyst, H., S. Wiggins, H., H. Cummings, J., 1982. Determination of the non-starch polysaccharides in plant foods by gas-liquid chromatography of constituent sugars as alditol acetates. *Analyst* 107, 307–318. <https://doi.org/10.1039/AN9820700307>
- Koko, A., Dr, Kouame, B., Anvoh, B.Y., 2014. COMPARATIVE STUDY ON PHYSICOCHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF CASSAVA ROOTS FROM THREE LOCAL CULTIVARS IN CÔTE D'IVOIRE.
- Levigne, S., Thomas, M., Ralet, M.-C., Quemener, B., Thibault, J.-F., 2002. Determination of the degrees of methylation and acetylation of pectins using a C18 column and internal standards. *Food Hydrocoll.* 16, 547–550. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0268-005X\(02\)00015-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0268-005X(02)00015-2)
- Liu, J., Bi, J., McClements, D.J., Liu, X., Yi, J., Lyu, J., Zhou, M., Verkerk, R., Dekker, M., Wu, X., Liu, D., 2020. Impacts of thermal and non-thermal processing on structure and functionality of pectin in fruit- and vegetable- based products: A review. *Carbohydr. Polym.* 250, 116890. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2020.116890>
- Liu, X., Renard, C.M.G.C., Bureau, S., Le Bourvellec, C., 2021. Revisiting the contribution of ATR-FTIR spectroscopy to characterize plant cell wall polysaccharides. *Carbohydr. Polym.* 262, 117935. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2021.117935>
- Morrison, I.M., 1972. A semi-micro method for the determination of lignin and its use in predicting the digestibility of forage crops. *J. Sci. Food Agric.* 23, 455–463. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.2740230405>
- Onitilo, M., Sanni, L., Daniel, I., Maziya-Dixon, B., Dixon, A., 2007. Physicochemical and functional properties of native starches from cassava varieties in Southwest Nigeria. *J. Food Agric. Environ.* 5.
- Renard, C.M.G.C., 2005. Variability in cell wall preparations: quantification and comparison of common methods. *Carbohydr. Polym.* 60, 515–522. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2005.03.002>
- Saeman, J.F., Moore, W., Mitchell, R., Millett, M.A., 1954. Techniques for the determination of pulp constituents by quantitative paper chromatography. *Tappi J.*
- Sajeev, M.S., Sreekumar, J., Unnikrishnan, M., Moorthy, S.N., Shanavas, S., 2010. Kinetics of thermal softening of cassava tubers and rheological modeling of the starch. *J. Food Sci. Technol.* 47, 507–518. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13197-010-0087-0>
- Talari, A.C.S., Martinez, M.A.G., Movasaghi, Z., Rehman, S., Rehman, I.U., 2017. Advances in Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy of biological tissues. *Appl. Spectrosc. Rev.* 52, 456–506. <https://doi.org/10.1080/05704928.2016.1230863>
- Zhang, P., Whistler, R.L., BeMiller, J.N., Hamaker, B.R., 2005. Banana starch: production, physicochemical properties, and digestibility—a review. *Carbohydr. Polym.* 59, 443–458. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2004.10.014>

7 APPENDICES

7.1 Annex: Neutral sugars of cell walls for cassava varieties

